

Jason Allen Greig advice on colored pencils for beginners and professional artists

Colored pencils are usually associated with childhood, but with the coloring book craze, it is clear that adults also love to use them; however, these tools do more than just color within lines. [Artists](#) use them regularly because they offer endless possibilities, especially for their shades. While many professional sets include many beautiful colors, you can use them in layers to create a greater dimension in your work.

Determining which are the [best colored pencils](#) can be a challenge. In the end, it depends on your preferences, but to put you on the right track, we have identified some of the best on the market. These brands are available online, making it easy to try different types without going bankrupt. It is important to find your favorites; if you take the time to discover the ones that work best with you, working will be more enjoyable.

How to determine the quality of colored pencils?

One of the most important aspects is, of course, color. Products for professionals and artists are generally of higher quality than those for students. In terms of colored pencils, this means that their shades will be deeper, making them look more vibrant on paper. Avoid muted or pale tones, since they have a lower quality due to having less pigment.

Another important feature is how well the pencil glides on the paper. Thanks to their ingredients, the best colored pencils move effortlessly as you drag them across the surface. If you're looking for top-notch pencils, look for oil-based ones instead of wax-based ones. Hard wax, in particular, can be brittle, making it more difficult to mix colors.

Prismacolor Premier is considered by many to be ideal for beginners as well as book colorists. They're low in price per pencil (\$ 0.60 when you buy this 150-piece set!) And they're made of soft wax; They combine well and their application feels like butter, so if you just bought your first coloring book, try these.